

Behaviour of *Mucuna Flagellepes* Leaves Extract in Corrosion Prevention Using Electrochemical Measurement

¹ADEBAYO Oluwafemi Lawrence and ¹ESAN Timothy Oluwaseun

¹Department of Chemical sciences, Bamidele Olumilua University of Education
Science and Technology, Ikere, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

adebayo.oluwafemi@bouesti.edu.ng

Abstract: *The potential application of naturally occurring materials as corrosion inhibitors is intriguing due to their affordability and environmental acceptability. This study uses electrochemical measurement to examine the inhibitory efficacy of Mucuna flagellepes leaf ethanol extract on the mild steel in an acidic medium. While the effect of pH and temperature variation of the acidic medium was investigated at a fixed concentration of the extract (10g/L), electrochemical measurement was performed using polarization cells of one litter capacity at varying concentrations of the extract between 2 and 10g/L. Based on concentration variation results, Mucuna flagellepes leaf extract would be able to prevent mild steel from corroding in acidic medium. As the extract concentration increased, the density of corrosion current (I_{cor}) decreased; the inhibitor solution containing 10 g/L showed the lowest I_{cor} value, with a maximum inhibition value of 74.50%. The results of varying the acidic medium's pH and temperature at a fixed concentration of the extract showed that, the mild steel's rate of corrosion increases with rising temperatures and falls with rising acidic solution pH respectively.*

Key words: *Behavior, Corrosion, Inhibition, investigate, Potential,*

1. Introduction

Corrosion is an unaffordable problem for many industries, For many years, corrosion engineers and scientists have been deeply interested in identifying and mitigating the costs associated with metal corrosion. This interest has only grown over time. Many industries have aggressively employed anti-corrosion materials, inhibitors, anodic/cathodic protection, protective coatings, corrosion inspection, and monitoring tools to prevent corrosion and lower the cost of metallic structures. (Lebrini, M.et al., 2011, Shein, A. B.; Denisova A.V. 2006; Asan, A. et al., 2006; Morad, M.S.; Kamal El-Dean, A.M., 2006). The use of corrosion inhibitors is a common and traditional corrosion protection method for metal storage. Even though many inhibitors have excellent inhibition activity, the majority are not safe for the environment. (Smith, L., 1999; Villamizar, W. et al., 2007, Villamizar, W. et al., 2006). The ability of substances to successfully lower the rate of metal corrosion when added at low concentrations is known as a corrosion inhibitor.(Deyab, M.A., 2007, Munoz, A. I. et al., Felhösi, I. et al., 2002). Based on the chemical structure of corrosion inhibitors, they can be divided into two categories: organic and

inorganic inhibitors (Quraishi, M. A.; Jamal, D., 2000; Raja, P. B.; Sethuraman, M.G.,2008). The development of the relationship between inorganic-organic corrosion inhibitors in different media has been the subject of numerous investigations recently (Zucchi, F.; Omar, I. 1985; Afidah, A.R. et al., 2008; Abdel-Gaber, A.M.,2009). However, chemical inhibitors that have been widely used in industries are made up of some hazardous substances that have drawn criticism for endangering both humanity and the environment. As a result, in recent years, this type of research has focused on the application and industrial-scale manufacturing of different environmentally friendly inhibitors (El-Etre, A.Y. , 2007; Oguzie, E.E., 2005; Haley, T.J. 1965; Ju, H. 2008). The current goal is to develop more affordable, environmentally friendly corrosion inhibitors using components derived from plant-based extracts, which are an easily renewable source. The current goal is to develop more affordable, environmentally friendly corrosion inhibitors using components derived from plant extracts, which are an easily sustainable source. The significant inhibition performance of sustainable corrosion inhibitors extracted from plants for metal corrosion control in acidic media has been investigated by a number of research groups. (Ahamad, I. et al., 2010; Doner, A. et. Al., 2011; Chen, W. et. Al., 2011; Djamel, D. et. Al., 2014; Kosari, A. et. Al., 2014; Seifzade, D. et. al., 2013). It has also been demonstrated that the nettle leaf extract inhibits corrosion when combined with inhibitory molecules such as quercetin, histamine, caffeine, and serotonin (Cano,E; et. Al., 2003; Moretti, G. et. al.,2004; Ostovari, A. et. al., 2009). Cichorium intybus L. and nettle leaf extract had an inhibitory potency of 26% and 51%, respectively. While there are reports of plant extracts being used as effective corrosion inhibitors for metals in a variety of media, the majority of these reports are not widely or inexpensively accessible. Thus, it would not be financially feasible to use them in industrial applications. As a result of the previous discussion, when selecting an inhibitor for a particular application, a number of factors must be taken into account, which involves high inhibition effectiveness, affordability, ease of accessibility, and—above all—environmental protection.(Olasehinde, E.F. et. al., 2015) Several experimental techniques, including the gravimetric method (Ostovari, A et. al., 2009), the potentiodynamic polarization technique (Al-Sehaibani, H. 2000) , the hydrogen evaluation method (Olusegun, K. A. et.al., 2007), and energy dispersed spectroscopy (EDS) (Ostovari, A., 2009), have been used to study the inhibitory efficiency of these renewable inhibitors. The leaves of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaves (Figure 1.1) were selected for this study for the reasons mentioned above. The leaves are a shrub that grows throughout Africa and is a member of the Euphorbiaceae family. In Nigeria and other African countries, the leaves are widely used in traditional medicine the leaves are greenish and trifoliate with leaflets broadly ovate, elliptic and unequal at the base. The plant has phytochemical components (Esan T.O, et. al., 2022; Adebayo, L. O, et. al., 2023) that can be used as corrosion, based on the literature review. In addition, the materials are widely accessible, cost-effective, and ecologically friendly (Olasehinde, E.F et. al., 2015).

Figure 1.1 : *Mucuna flagellepes* C. leaves (<https://en.wikipedia.org>,2020)

2. Methodology

2.1 Preparation of plant sample

The leaves of *Mucuna flagellepes* were cleaned, allowed to dry at room temperature, subsequently ground and sieved through an 850 μ m sieve. To obtain the dried sample of *Mucuna flagellepes* leave concentrate, 50g of the powdered sample was immersed in ethanol with continuous stirring for 72 hours. The filtrate was then squeezed through a 0.25 μ m filter and heated to 60° C in a water bath beneath a fume cupboard (Adebayo O.L et. al., 2019; Adebayo, O.L. et. al., 2019). Before being used, the dried extracts were kept in a brown bottle at room temperature.

Received: 2 May 2024

Revised: 17 May 2024

Accepted: 30 May 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

329

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11395610>

2.2 Mild steel preparation

The working electrode, mild steel, was procured from Universal Steel Company in Ogba Lagos and meticulously sliced into numerous cylindrical electrodes. Before being used, the cylindrical electrodes were cleaned with distilled water, dried with nitrogen gas, and stored in devoid of moisture desiccators using a struer polishing machine (Figure 2.1) that contained emery paper to produce a mirror-finish sample (Davi, B.S. and Rajandran, S., 2011).

Figure 2.1: Struers Polishing equipment (Dap-7: ID 2361)

2.3 Electrochemical measurement

The pH and temperature variations of the acidic medium, along with varying extract concentrations ranging from 2 to 10 g/L, were taken into account during the electrochemical assessment experiment. A polarization cell with a single litter capacity was used for the experiment (Figure

2.2). The reference electrode, composed of saturated calomel electrode (SCE), the counter electrode, composed of platinum electrode, and the functioning electrode, composed of mild steel, make up the cell.

Figure 2.2 : Electrochemical cells

3. RESULTS

3.1 Concentration studies

The polarization parameters and Tafel plot, including corrosion current densities (I_{cor}), corrosion potentials (E_{cor}), cathodic Tafel slope (β_c), anodic Tafel slope (β_a), polarization resistance (R_p), corrosion rate, and a percentage of inhibition efficiency $\eta_T(\%)$, are displayed in Figure 3.1 and Table 3.1, respectively, following the electrochemical measurement of the mild steel corrosion rate in 1M HCl with and without varying concentrations of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaf ethanol extract at room temperature.

$$\eta_T (\%) = \frac{I_{cor}^o - I_{cor}}{I_{cor}^o} \dots\dots 3.1$$

where the corrosion current densities in combination with and without *Mucuna flagellepes* leaf extract have the following values: I_{cor}^o and I_{cor}

Figure 3.1: Polarization curve for mild steel in 1.0M HCl solution in the absence and presence of various concentration of ethanol extract of air dried *Mucuna flagellepes* leaves

Table 3.1: Corrosion parameters for mild steel in the absence and presence of different concentration of ethanol extract of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaves at room temperature.

Conc. (g/L)	ba(v/dec)	bc(v/dec)	I _{cor} (A/cm ²)	P _R	CR (mm/y)	E _{cor}	I.E (%)
Blank	0.372	0.266	6.51 E-04	53.66	7.532	-0.465	-
2	0.358	0.224	5.00 E-04	141.8	5.788	-0.46	23.2
4	0.217	0.212	3.54E-04	143.4	3.881	-0.459	45.62
6	0.188	0.209	2.96E-04	151.5	3.422	-0.456	54.53
8	0.185	0.204	1.78E-04	225.9	2.061	-0.456	72.35
10	0.12	0.165	1.66E-04	380.2	1.915	-0.454	74.5

As the concentration of the extract increases from 2–10 g/L, the corrosion parameters (Table 3.1) show a decrease in the corrosion current (I_{cor}) density, and the highest concentration studied yielded the maximum inhibition efficiency (74.50%) of the extract. Additionally, the values of the mild steel's polarization resistance increased as the extract's concentration did. The *Mucuna flagellepes* leaf extract's adsorption on mild steel surfaces, which increases with extract concentration and also inhibits corrosion, is responsible for the decrease in corrosion current density and the rise in polarization resistance of the material as the concentration of the extract the mild steel electrode's attack with acid (Adebayo, O.L., et al., 2019). An inhibitor is classified as cathodic or anodic if its shift in E_{cor} from the uninhibited acid solution's E_{cor} is greater than 85 mV (Fu H., 2009; Ferreira et al., 2004). According to this study, the maximum shift of E_{cor} is 11 mV, suggesting that *Mucuna flagellepes* leaf ethanol extract functions as a mixed inhibitor to protect mild steel in acidic media.

3.2 pH Variation

The effect of pH variation in the acidic solution on the rate of mild steel corrosion at a fixed concentration (10g/L) of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaf extract was measured using Tafel polarization, which entails calculating Tafel curves. Figure 3.2 and Table 3.2, respectively, present the Tafel plots and the corrosion data collected at different acidic medium pH levels. The outcome showed that when the acidic solution's pH increased from 2 to 12, both the anodic and cathodic current densities decreased. The ethanol extract of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaves functions as an electrolyte because of the observed positive shift in the corrosion potentials and the decrease in both anodic and cathodic current density with an increase in pH.

Additionally, a close examination of the plot depicting the mild steel corrosion rate versus pH (Figure 3.3) revealed that the corrosion rate of mild steel falls as pH rises, and that this decline becomes more pronounced as pH levels rise from 2 to 6. The mild steel's corrosion rate at the highest pH under investigation varies negligibly between pH values of 8 and 10. The mild steel's surface partial passivation with Fe_2O_3 is responsible for the observed minimum corrosion rate of the studied mild steel at higher pH.

Figure 3.2: Tafel plot showing effect of pH variation of 1.0M HCl solution in the presence of 10g of ethanol extract of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaves.

3.2: Corrosion parameters for mild steel at various pH of the acidic solution at fixed concentration of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaves extract.

pH	Conc.	b_a	b_c	$I_{cor}(A/cm^2)$	R_p	CR(mm/y)	E_{cor}
2	10g/L	0.431	143.01	5.54E-04	146.7	6.122	-0.458
4	10g/L	0.343	38.401	3.73 E-04	226.5	2.043	-0.454
6	10g/L	0.206	5.746	3.13 E-04	314.2	2.011	-0.454
8	10g/L	0.141	0.199	2.74 4-04	366.3	1.761	-0.454
10	10g/L	0.098	0.186	7.45 E-05	442.6	1.487	-0.426
12	10g/L	0.091	0.177	5.62 E-05	743.2	0.956	-0.407

Figure 3.3: Plot of Corrosion rate of mild steel against pH variation at fixed concentration of ethanol extract of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaves extract.

3.3 Temperature Variation:

Figures 3.4 and Table 3.4, respectively, display the polarization curves and corrosion parameters, such as corrosion potentials (E_{cor}), corrosion currents (I_{cor}), density, anodic Tafel slope (b_a), cathodic Tafel slope (b_c), and polarization resistance, obtained at fixed concentrations (10g/L) of ethanol extract of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaves in 1.0M HCl at different temperatures on mild steel. The table demonstrated that, although the corrosion rate increased with temperature, the mild steel's polarization resistance decreased as temperature rose.

According to Xi-lan J. (2018), the desorption of leaf extracts from the mild steel's surface allowed for an increase in the corrosion rate of the material as a result of a rise in temperature, which is why the mild steel's polarization resistance decreased and its rate of corrosion increased.

Figure 3.4: Tafel plots of mild steel specimen in 1.0M HCl at different temperature and fixed concentration of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaves extract.

Table 3.4: Corrosion parameters for mild steel in 1.0M HCl at different temperature and fixed concentration of ethanol extract *Mucuna flagellepes* leaves.

Temp. (°C)	Inh. Conc. (g)	ba(v/dec)	bc(v/dec)	I Cor(Acm ⁻²)	R _p (ohms)	CR (mm/y)	E _{cor}
20	10	0.238	0.146	1.43 E-04	331.2	1.65	-0.479
30	10	0.291	0.155	1.46 E-04	324.4	1.685	-0.520
40	10	0.304	0.162	1.50 E-04	312.4	1.737	-0.522
50	10	0.352	0.167	1.84E -04	276.0	2.13	-0.531
60	10	0.356	0.189	2.18 E-04	267.9	2.526	-0.533
70	10	0.380	0.259	2.57 E-04	205.7	2.973	-0.542

Received: 2 May 2024
 Revised: 17 May 2024
 Accepted: 30 May 2024
 Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11395610>

4. Conclusion

Using electrochemical measurement, the behavior of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaf extract in preventing mild steel from corroding was investigated at different extract concentrations as well as variations in the acidic medium's pH and temperature. The results showed that the ethanol extract of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaves had the maximum inhibitory activity when it was at the highest concentration under investigation. The mild steel's corrosion rate increases with temperature but decreases with increasing pH, according to the corrosion parameters measured after the acidic medium's temperature and pH were varied. Furthermore, the extract of *Mucuna flagellepes* leaves has an Ecor value between -0.465 and -0.454 mV, indicating that the inhibitors function as mixed-type inhibitors.

References

- Abdel-Gaber, A.M.; Masoud, M.S. Khalil, E.A.; Shehata, E.E., Electrochemical study on the effect of Schiff base and its cobalt complex on the acid corrosion of steel, *Corro. Sci.* **2009**, 51(12), 3021– 3024. DOI: [10.1016/j.corsci.2009.08.025](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2009.08.025)
- Abdel-Gaber, A.M; Abd-EL-Nabey, B. A Saa dawy, M., The role of acid anion on the inhibition of the acidic corrosion of steel by lupine extract. *Corro. Sci.* **2009**, 51(5), 1038–1042, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2009.03.003>
- Adebayo, L. O, **Esan***, T. O, Osasona, I, Emmanuel, A. V; (2023) Organic Constituents in Air-Dried Alchornea laxiflora Leaves (AALL) Extract: Corrosion Remediation, Isolation and Structural Elucidation. *Adv. J. Chem. A*, 2023, 6(3), 225-243. DOI: 10.22034/AJCA.2023.393053.13632015. http://dx.doi.org/10.15242/IICBE.C6140_02.
- Adebayo O.L., Olasehinde F.E., Lajide L. & Oloruntoba D.T. (2019). Comparative analysis of air dried *alchornea laxiflora* leaves (AALL) extracted with different solvents on corrosion inhibition efficiency of mild steel in acidic media. *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Innovation*. 3(3), page 208-216.
- Adebayo, O.L, Olasehinde, F.E., Lajide L., Oloruntoba, D.T. & Ajayi, M.G. (2019). Studies on Thermal Stability, Shelf Life and Electrochemical Measurement of Methanol Extract of Air Dried *Alchornea Laxiflora* Leaves in Corrosion Prevention. *American Journal of Materials Synthesis and Processing*. 4(2) page 68-74.
- Afidah, A.R.; Rocca, E.; Steinmetz, J.; Kassim, M.J., Inhibitive action of mangrove tannin and phosphoric acid on pre - rusted steel via electrochemical method, *Corro. Sci.* **2008**, 50(6), 1546–1550, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2008.02.013>.
- Ahamad, I.; Prasad, R.; Quraishi, M. A., Thermodynamic, electrochemical and Quantum chemical investigation of some schiff bases as corrosion inhibitors for mild steel in hydrochloric acid solution, *Corro. Sci.* **2010**, 52(3), 933–942. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2009.11.016>

- Al-Sehaibani, H.; Evaluation of Extracts of Henna Leaves as Environmentally Friendly Corrosion Inhibitors for Metals. *Mat. Sci. and Eng. Tech.* **2000**, 31, 1060-1063, [https://doi.org/10.1002/1521-4052\(200012\)31:12<1060::AID-MAWE1060>3.0.CO;2-K](https://doi.org/10.1002/1521-4052(200012)31:12<1060::AID-MAWE1060>3.0.CO;2-K).
- Asan, A.; Soylu, S.; Kiyak, T.; Yildirim, F.; Oztas, S., Investigation on some Schiff bases as corrosion inhibitors for mild steel. *Corros. Sci.* **2006**, 48(12), 3933-3944, DOI: [10.1016/j.corsci.2006.04-001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2006.04-001).
- Bethencourt, M.; Botana, F. J.; Calvino, J. J. Marcos, M.; Rodriguez-Chacon, M.A., Lanthanide compounds as environmentally-friendly corrosion inhibitors of aluminium alloys: a review, *Corro. Sci.* **1998**, 40 (11), 1803-1819, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-938X\(98\)00077-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-938X(98)00077-8)
- Chen, W.; Luo, H.Q.; Li, N.B., Inhibition effects of 2,5-dimercapto-1,3,4 thiadiazole on the corrosion of mild steel in sulphuric acid solution, *Corro. Sci.* **2011**, 53(10), 3356–3365, DOI: [10.1016/j.corsci.2011.06.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2011.06.013)
- Cano, E.; Pinilla, P.; Polo, J. L.; Bastidas J. M., Copper corrosion inhibition by fast green, fuchsin acid and basic compounds in citric acid solution. *Mat. And corro.* 2003, 54, 222-228. <http://doi.org/10.1002/maco.200390050>.
- Davi, B.S. and Rajandran, S. (2011). Influence of garlic extract on the inhibition efficiency of trisodium citrate – Zn²⁺ system. *International Journal of Chemical Science and Technology* 1: 79 – 87.
- Deyab, M.A., Effect of cationic surfactant and inorganic anions on the electrochemical behaviour of carbon steel in formation water. *Corro. Sci.* **2007**, 49(5), 2315-2328, DOI: [10.1016/j.corsci.2006.10.035](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2006.10.035)
- Doner, A.; Solmaz, R.; Ozcan, M.; Kardas. G., Experimental and theoretical studies of thiazoles as corrosion inhibitors for mild steel in sulphuric acid solution. *Corro. Sci.* **2011**, 53, 2902–2913, DOI: [10.1016/j.corsci.2011.05.027](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2011.05.027)
- Djamel, D.; Tahar, D.; Saifi, I.; Salah, C., Adsorption and corrosion inhibition of new synthesized thiophene Schiff base on mild steel X52 in HCl and H₂SO₄ solutions, *Corro. Sci.* **2014**, 79, 50–58, DOI: [10.1016/j.corsci.2013.10.025](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2013.10.025)
- Esan T.O**, Oyeneyin, O. E, Olanipekun, A.D, Ipinloju, N. (2022), Corrosion Inhibitive Potentials of some amino acid derivatives of 1,4-naphthoquinone-DFT Calculations. *Advance Journal of Chemistry section-A*, 5(4), <http://dx.doi.org/10.22034/ajca.2022.353882.1321>
- El-Etre, A.Y., Inhibition of acid corrosion of carbon steel using aqueous extract of olive leaves, *J. of Colloid and Interf. Sci.* **2007**, 314(2), 578–583. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2007.05.077>
- [10] Felhösi, I.; Kálmán, E.; Póczik, P., Corrosion Protection by Self-Assembly. *Russian J. of Electrochem.* **2002**, 38, 230-237, DOI: [10.1023/A:1014718320345](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1014718320345)
- Ferreira E.S., Giacomelli C., Giacomelli F.C. & Spinell A. (2004). Evaluation of the inhibitor effect of L-ascorbic acid on the corrosion of mild steel. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*. 83(1) page 129-134.

- Fu H. (2009). Synergism between red tetrazolium and uracil on the corrosion of cold rolled steel in H_2SO_4 solution. *Corrosion Science*. 51(6) page 1344-1355.
- Haley, T.J., Pharmacology and Toxicology of the Rare Earth Elements. *J. of Pharmac. Sci.* **1965**, 54(5), 633–670. [doi:10.1002/jps.2600540502](https://doi.org/10.1002/jps.2600540502)
- Ju, H.; Kai, Z. P.; Li, Y., Aminic nitrogen-bearing polydentate Schiff base compounds as corrosion inhibitors for iron in acidic media: A quantum chemical calculation. *Corro. Sci.***2008**, 50(3), 865–871, DOI:[10.1016/j.corsci.2007.10.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2007.10.009)
- Kosari, A.; Moayed, M. H.; Davoodi, A.;Pervizi, R.; Momeni, M.; Eshghi, H.; Moradi, H., Electrochemical and quantum chemical assessment of two organic compounds from pyridine derivatives as corrosion inhibitors for mild steel in HCl solution under stagnant condition and hydrodynamic flow. *Corro. Sci.* **2014**, 78, 138–150, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2013.09.009>
- Lebrini, M.; Robert, F.; Lecante, A.; Roos C., Corrosion inhibition of Carbon steel in 1M hydrochloric acid medium by alkaloids extract from Oxandra asbeckii plant. *Corros. Sci.***2011**, 53(2), 687–695, [DOI: 10.1016/j.corsci.2010.10.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2010.10.006).
- Morad, M.S.; Kamal El-Dean, A.M., 2,2'- Dithiobis(3-cyano-4,6-dimethylpyridine): A new class of acid corrosion inhibitors for mild steel. *Corros. Sci.* **2006**, 48(11),3398- 3412. [DOI:10.1016/j.corsci.2005.12.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2005.12.006).
- Moretti, G.; Guidi, F., Grion, G., Tryptamine as a green iron corrosion inhibitor in 0.5M deaerated sulphuric acid. *Corr. Sci.* **2004**, 46, 387-403, DOI [10.1016/S0010-938X\(03\)00150-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-938X(03)00150-1).
- Munoz, A. I. ; Anton, J.G.; Guinon, V; Herranz, V. P., Inhibition effect of chromate on the passivation and pitting corrosion of a duplex stainless steel in LiBr solutions using electrochemical techniques. *Corros. Sci.* 49(8), **2007**, 3200-3225, DOI:[10.1016/j.corsci.2007.03.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2007.03.002)
- Oguzie, E.E., Corrosion inhibition of mild steel in hydrochloric acid solution by methylene blue dye, *Mater. Letters* **2005**, 59(8-9), 1076 -1079. DOI:[10.1016/j.matlet.2004.12.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2004.12.009)
- Olasehinde, E.F.; Ogunjobi, J. K.; Akinlosotu, O. M.; Omogbehin, S. A., Investigation of the Inhibitive Properties of *Alchornea laxiflora* leaves on the Corrosion of Mild Steel in HCl: Thermodynamics and Kinetic Studies, *J. of American Sci.***2015**, 11(1s), 32-39,<http://www.jofamericanscience.org/journals/am-sci>.
- Ostovari, A.; Hoseinie, S.M.; Peikari, M.;Shadizadeh,S.R.; Hashemi, S. J., Corrosion inhibition of mild steel in 1 M HCl solution by henna extract: A comparative study of the inhibition by henna and its constituents (Lawsone, Gallic acid, α -D Glucose and Tannic acid), *Corr. Sci.* **2009**,51(9),1935– 1949, DOI:[10.1016/j.corsci.2009.05.024](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2009.05.024).
- Olusegun, K. A.; Ofoka, N. C.; Eno, E.; Nwinuka, N. M., Eco-friendly corrosion inhibitors: The inhibitive action of Delonix Regia extract for the corrosion of aluminium in acidic

- media. *Anticorrosion method and mater.* **2007**, 54(4), 219-224, DOI:[10.1108/00035590710762357](https://doi.org/10.1108/00035590710762357).
- Quraishi, M. A.; Jamal, D., Technical Note: CAHMT- A new and Eco – Friendly Acidizing Corrosion Inhibitor. *Corro.* **2000**, 56(10), 983, DOI:[10.5006/1.3294388](https://doi.org/10.5006/1.3294388)
- Raja, P. B.; Sethuraman, M.G., Natural Products as Corrosion Inhibitor for Metals in Corrosive Media. *Material Letters.* **2008**, 62, 113-116 DOI:[10.1016/j.matlet.2007.04.079](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2007.04.079)
- Rodriguez-Valdez, L.M.; Villamizar, W.; Casales, M.; Gonzalez-Rodriguez, J.G.; Martinez-Villafane, A., Computational simulations of the molecular structure and corrosion properties of amidoethyl, aminoethyl and hydroxyethyl imidazolines inhibitors. *Corros. Sci.* **2006**, 48(12), 4053-4064, DOI:[10.1016/j.corsci.2006.05.036](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2006.05.036)
- Seifzade, D.; Basharnavaz, H.; Bezaatpour, A., A Schiff base compound as effective corrosion inhibitor for magnesium in acidic media. *Mater. Chem. and Phys.* **2013**, 138(2-3), 794-802, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2012.12.063>
- Shein, A. B.; Denisova A.V., Choice of Effective Corrosion Inhibitors for Acid Treatment of Wells. *Protec. of Metals.* **2006**, 42(1),34-37, DOI:[10.1134/50033173206010061](https://doi.org/10.1134/50033173206010061).
- Smith, L., Control of corrosion in oil and gas production tubing. *British Corros J.* **1999**, 34(4), 247-253. DOI:10.1179/000705999101500905.
- Villamizar, W.; Casales, M.; Gonzalez-Rodriguez, J. G.; Martinez, L., CO₂ corrosion inhibition by hydroxyl ethyl, amino ethyl, and aminoethyl imidazolines in water oil mixtures. *J. of Solid State Electrochem.* **2007** 619- 629. DOI:[10.1007/s10008-006-0208-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10008-006-0208-x)
- Xi-lan Jiang, Chuan Lai, Zhen Xiang, Ya-fei Yang, Bang-long Tan, Zhong-qiu Long, Lin-peng Liu, Yun-tian Gu, Wen-jian Yang, Xia Chen: Study on the Extract of RaphanusSativus L as Green Corrosion Inhibitor for Steel in HCl Solution, *int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 2018, 133224-3234, doi:10.20964/2018.04/16.
- Zucchi, F.; Omar, I., Plant extracts as corrosion inhibitors of mild steel in HCl solutions, *Surf. Tech.* **1985**, 24(4), 391–399, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0376-4583\(85\)90057-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0376-4583(85)90057-3)